

Developing and promoting search engine literacy in primary education

Melanie Platz, Saarland University, 66123 Saarbrücken, Germany

Friederike Klan, German Aerospace Center (DLR), 07745 Jena, Germany

Alexander Decker, Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt, 85049 Ingolstadt, Germany

Abstract

Students use the internet every day, but the lack of transparency regarding information filtering employed by search engines, user profiling done based on search queries, as well as the design of the user interfaces of popular platforms, lead to increasing immaturity in user behavior and low-risk awareness concerning privacy. This begins with the choice of a search engine. As early as elementary school age, children need the competence, both in the school context and in everyday life, to search for information accurately, evaluate search results, and assess possible risks from disclosing personal data. However, this is not explicitly addressed in previous school concepts. In this paper, we present the first ideas for a teaching concept for promoting search engine literacy (SEL) in primary education.

WHAT IS SEARCH ENGINE LITERACY?

Already in primary school, children are expected to conduct internet searches [1; 2]. Competent searching poses complex challenges, the mastering of which requires a corresponding competence - search engine literacy. To define search engine literacy (SEL), the concepts of information literacy and search literacy are considered [3]:

- **Information literacy** is the ability to understand when information is needed, to seek information efficiently, and evaluate and use information appropriately. It also includes integrating new information with prior knowledge and using it legally, economically, socially, and ethically correct to achieve goals.
- **Search literacy** is a specific aspect of information literacy. It relates directly to the process of obtaining information and refers to the ability to find and access the desired information to satisfy information needs efficiently and effectively.
- Achieving accurate search results requires **search engine literacy**, which is the knowledge of how search engines work and the following: findability, linguistic functions, query language, and ranking [4].

However, search engine literacy can only be achieved inadequately by "learning-by-doing" in the sense of

discovery learning - its acquisition must instead be supported in a targeted manner. To implement the topic search engines into the primary school curriculum, fundamental ideas must be identified and linked directly to the existing curriculum [5].

STATE OF THE ART: SEARCH AND INFORMATION LITERACY IN SCHOOL

We address the primary level to contribute to the early education of self-confident and self-determined use of search engines. Primary school children mostly use search engines [6; 7] without knowing or questioning how they work [8]. International studies have investigated the promotion of various aspects of information literacy [9; 10]. Specifically for search literacy, individual concepts exist, including co-creative approaches [11], that aim to help users understand a search process [8; 12; 13]. Due to their complexity, these are less suitable for primary education or only deal with the operation of a search engine [14]. The internal functional principles remain a "black box". Research on the assessment of privacy and disclosure of personal data among children rarely focuses on search engines and risks by deriving user profiles [15].

Surveys with teachers [16] show that promoting information literacy is challenging to implement in the classroom and that integrative, resource-saving concepts are needed. The development and acquisition of search engine literacy cannot be assigned to a single learning area [1].

TEACHING CONCEPT

Consequently, we provide a concept that can be used in elementary school lessons in combination with traditional teaching topics without taking up additional teaching time.

We were able to show that modules to promote SEL can be developed by linking to the traditional content of mathematics instruction [5] and that learning with and about media [17] can be supported by specific elementary school-appropriate digital environments [18; 19], and that co-creative design of digital applications is promising [20]. Observations from the first pilot studies point to gender-specific effects. SEL can be promoted at three levels that address aspects that are interrelated (see figure 1).

Figure 1: Three levels of SEL.

For the well-founded penetration of a concept, we transferred the idea of [21] (topic area "algorithms") to "search engines" and extended it by a reflection (see figure 2):

Figure 2: Model for the theoretically founded penetration of a concept; originally on the topic of "algorithms" [21], here transferred to "search engines" and extended by a reflection.

Focusing on the aspect of ranking, an example for the application of this model in primary school in connection with traditional teaching topics in mathematics could be as follows:

Ranking is about putting the search results found in a sensible order, so that the relevant results are displayed first and the less relevant results further down the list. This involves sorting by descending relevance, i.e., the higher a hit is in the list, the more relevant it is. Search engines do not disclose their ranking procedures, yet six areas have emerged that determine how results are ranked: (1) text-

specific factors, (2) popularity, (3) recency, (4) locality, (5) personalization, and (6) technical ranking factors [22].

In this example, we focus on (1): Text statistics are used to compare search queries and documents. The first assumption in text statistics ranking is that the entered search term occurs in the document. One assumes that the searcher wants to find the entered term in the document. With this first step, all other documents are excluded, i.e., a first narrowing down of the search result. While the entire index must first be searched, a base set to which the further ranking factors are applied is now determined. All further operations are only performed on this smaller set [22]. First,

one could assume that a document in which the search term occurs particularly frequently is more relevant than one in which the search term occurs less frequently. The document containing the most frequent search term would appear first in the list.

- Initial Example:** To treat this first idea of ranking based on frequency determination at the primary school level, a search of text sections of the same length for a specific search term can be carried out as a starting example. Initially, texts of the same length are used because absolute frequencies are dealt with first, and longer texts would have a better chance of containing a word frequently.
- The initial abstraction** to this simple ranking based on frequency determination would be, in this case, for example: A ranking of search results for a search term can be created by first excluding the texts, mathematical objects, etc., that do not contain the search term. Afterward, the order in which the texts, mathematical objects, etc., are to be displayed can be determined using frequency determination. The text, mathematical object, etc., in which the search term is found most often, comes first, the text, mathematical object, etc., in which the search term occurs second most often, comes second, and so on.
- Concretizations** regarding primary school mathematics could, for example, look as follows:
 - On the set of numbers up to 20, "large, even" is searched for. (Even numbers are divisible by 2 without remainders.) In the first step, all odd numbers are excluded. In the second step, the remaining even numbers are arranged in descending order (as 2 fits or is contained most often in 20, etc.): (20, 18, 16, 14, 12, 8, 6, 4, 2).
 - On the set of geometric solids {cube, sphere, cone, triangular-based pyramid, cylinder} "face" is searched. Each of the geometric solids has faces. They are arranged in descending order according to the number of faces: (cube, triangular-based pyramid, cylinder, cone, sphere).
- For reflection,** the set we are looking at can be changed; for example, the determination of an exact order and the comparability of the objects can be made more complex to initiate the consideration of structural information in documents, if necessary. In this way, a discussion can be prompted about what "meaningful" search results are that help the searcher: the idea of quality control can be stimulated (see, for example figure 3). For one's search, it can be deduced that the formulation of the search query is essential and that not only the first hits should be considered but also subsequent ones since the ranking "is always only one of many possible algorithmic views of the contents of the World Wide Web" ([22], p. 93).

Figure 3: "large number" and "faces"

Based on this idea, existing concepts of SEL can be transferred to the primary school level. For example, it could be shown that an interactive visualization of a filter bubble increases the awareness of the concept and the comprehensibility of the filtering mechanism [23]. The Webfinder tool (<https://iddocs.fr/webfinder/index.php>; see a screenshot in figure 4) was developed for use in secondary education, and it allows us to understand the steps of classification as well as methods of automatic processing [8]. It additionally enables understanding of the criteria for ranking information according to the principles of relevance (number of occurrences related to the query), popularity (number of visits), and familiarity (number of links). This also helps learners understand an algorithm with a weighting system.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the Webfinder tool.

Among others, mathematical concepts can describe and explain how search engines work. A key element in promoting SEL is reflecting on one's actions due to engagement with algorithmic selection and sorting functions [24]. Co-creative approaches can contribute to this in particular [11; 25] and develop great potential in the context of SEL if school challenges (time constraints, class sizes, teachers' concerns; [26]) are overcome.

The underlying concepts or fundamental ideas of the topic "search engines" must be identified to address all facets of SEL. Several teaching units are developed in connection to traditional contents treated in primary school on two levels:

1. The question "How does a search engine work?" is focused on the first level. Through relation, reflection, and argumentation, "guidelines" for optimized search are derived: "What do I need to consider when using search engines?; Why is it important?"

- Through problem-solving and reasoning, search strategies are developed (2nd Big6-Stage, [27]) "How do I get the best search results?; Which strategy fits when?"

Teaching units addressing the first level were developed and tested with pupils as a basis for the second level by primary school student teachers at Saarland University. The teaching units are published as Open Educational Resources at Wikiversity (currently only available in the German language):

https://de.wikiversity.org/wiki/Open-Source4School/Lernumgebungen_zur_Informatischen_Bildung_im_Mathematikunterricht_der_Primarstufe#Search_Engine_Literacy

Preliminary results of the teaching experiments show that the primary school children are very knowledgeable and understand a lot. But there are also some challenges: e.g., "meaningful" input into the search engine was not easy for the children: Instead of only entering the relevant search terms, the children tried to form complete sentences (e.g., instead of "gift", "I want a gift" was entered).

The teaching concept for promoting SEL is (further) developed by utilizing Design Science Research (DSR). The Dortmund Model (subject didactic development research

on diagnosis-guided teaching-learning processes for research and further development of instruction) [28] is combined with the DSR Methodology Process (research and further development of Information Systems Research) [29] to be able to productively use synergy effects of both approaches for the development of technology-supported learning environments [30]. By linking and transferring this idea to other primary school subjects like science and ethics and reflecting on the effect of overcoming the black box effect (in the sense of world-encompassing learning with and about search engines), critical basic education in information and communication technology is promoted. Through such networking, the broader social dimensions of SEL leading to questions in the context of democracy and social participation can be addressed.

CONCLUSION

A teaching concept for the promotion of search engine literacy (SEL) in primary schools is developed in close cooperation with the educational practitioners. Its effectiveness will first be investigated in selected German student laboratories, then evaluated nationwide and finally transferred to schools (see figure 5).

Figure 5: Project phases.

REFERENCES

- [1] KMK. *Strategie der Kultusministerkonferenz „Bildung in der digitalen Welt“* (Beschluss vom 08.12.2016). Berlin: Eigendruck; 2016. Abrufbar unter: https://www.kmk.org/fileadmin/pdf/PresseUndAktuelles/2018/Digitalstrategie_2017_mit>Weiterbildung.pdf.
- [2] GDSU. *Positionspapier Sachunterricht und Digitalisierung. Erarbeitet von der AG Medien & Digitalisierung der Gesellschaft für Didaktik des Sachunterrichts*; 2021. Abrufbar unter: https://gdsu.de/sites/default/files/PDF/GDSU_2021_Positionspapier_Sachunterricht_und_Digitalisierung_deutsch.de.pdf.
- [3] Karatassis, I. A gamification framework for enhancing search literacy. *Proceedings of the 6th BCS-IRSG Symposium on Future Directions in Information Access* 2015; 6: 3–6.
- [4] Fuhr, N. *Internet search engines – Lecture script for the course in SS 2014*, 2014. Available online at http://www.is.inf.uni-due.de/courses/ir_ss14/ISMs_1-7.pdf
- [5] Platz M, Müller L, Niehaus E, Müller S. Modules for Open Search in Mathematics Teaching. In *Proceedings of the 3rd OSSYM, CERN*. 2021. Abrufbar unter: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5772576>.
- [6] Medienpädagogischer Forschungsverbund Südwest. Kinder, Internet, Medien (KIM). *Basisuntersuchung zum Medienumgang 6- bis 13-Jähriger in Deutschland*. Mpfs; 2020. Abrufbar unter https://www.mpfs.de/fileadmin/files/Studien/KIM/2020/KIM-Studie2020_WEB_final.pdf.
- [7] Feil Ch, Gieger Ch, Grobbing A. *Projekt: Informationsverhalten von Kindern im Internet – eine empirische Studie zur Nutzung von Suchmaschinen*. München: Deutsches Jugendinstitut; 2013. Abrufbar unter: https://www.dji.de/fileadmin/user_upload/www-kinderseiten/898/1-BMBF-Fkz%2001PF08017.pdf.
- [8] Le Deuff O. Search engine literacy. In *Proceedings of the European Conference on Information Literacy* 2017; 359–365.
- [9] Aharony N, Gur H. The relationships between personality, perceptual, cognitive and technological variables and students' level of information literacy. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science* 2017; 51(2): 527–544.
- [10] Beltran-Sanchez J A, Lopez R I G, Ramirez-Montoya M S, Quintana J T. Factors influencing the Integration of the Digital Literacy and Inclusion Program into Primary School Teaching. *Revista Electronica De Investigacion Educativa* 2019, 21: 1–11.
- [11] Beheshti J, AlGhamdi M J, Cole C, Abuhimed D, Lamoureux I. Designing an Intervention Tool for Students with Students. *New Directions in Children's and Adolescents' Information Behavior Research*. *Library and Information Science* 2017, 10: 295–331.
- [12] Nuxoll F. *Medienwelten Grundschule Arbeitsheft 3/4*. Braunschweig: Westermann; 2021
- [13] Wilson M L, Ye C, Twidale M B, Grasse H. Search literacy: Learning to search to learn. In *Proceedings of SAL@ SIGIR*; 2016; Pisa, Italy.
- [14] Moreno-Morilla C, Guzman-Simon F, Garcia-Jimenez E. Digital and information literacy inside and outside Spanish primary education schools. *Learning Culture and Social Interaction* 2021, 28(1): 1–21.
- [15] Stoilova M, Nandagiri R, Livingstone S. Children's Understanding of Personal Data and Privacy Online – A Systematic Evidence Mapping. *Inf Commun Soc* 2019; 6(1): 1–19.
- [16] Batool S H, Webber S. Mapping the state of information literacy education in primary schools: The case of Pakistan. *Libr Inf Sci Res* 2019; 41(2): 123–131.
- [17] Peschel M. Welterschließung als sachunterrichtliches Lernen mit und über digitale Medien - Lernen mit und über digitale Medien als Ausgangspunkt einer umfassenden Sachbildung. In: *Thumel M, Kammerl R, Irion T, Hrsg. Digitale Bildung im Grundschulalter – Grundsatzfragen zum Primat des Pädagogischen*. München: kopaed; 2020. S. 341–355.
- [18] Bach S. *Subjektiver Kompetenzerwerb von Schülerinnen und Schülern beim unterrichtlichen Einsatz von kidi-Maps - Eine Studie zum Einsatz digitaler Karten am Beispiel von kidi-Maps im Vergleich zu analogen Karten bei Schülerinnen und Schülern einer vierten Jahrgangsstufe im geographisch-orientierten Sachunterricht*. Saarbrücken: Universität des Saarlandes; 2018.
- [19] Schirra S, Peschel M. Recherchieren, Dokumentieren und Präsentieren mit kidipedia im Zeitalter von Tablet & Co. In: *Peschel M, Irion T, Hrsg. Neue Medien in der Grundschule 2.0. Grundlagen – Konzepte - Perspektiven*. Frankfurt am Main: Grundschulverband; 2016. S. 235–246.
- [20] Klan F, Kyba C, Schulte-Römer N, Kuechly H. Co-Designing Mobile Applications for Citizen Science Projects - First Results of the Nachtlicht-BÜHNE Project. In *Proceedings of the 3rd Intl. ECSA Citizen Science Conference*; 2020; Online.
- [21] Eitzold, H., Noack, S. & Jurk, A. (2019). *Algorithmen im Alltag. Leitfaden für Lehrerinnen und Lehrer. Teil 1: Hintergrund und Theorie*. *Digitales Lernen Grundschule, Universität Potsdam*. Abgerufen von https://dlgs.uni-potsdam.de/sites/default/files/u3/Leitfaden_Algorithmen_Teil_1.pdf
- [22] Lewandowski, D. *Suchmaschinen verstehen*. Berlin/Heidelberg: Springer Vieweg; 2021.
- [23] Nagulendra S, Vassileva J. Understanding and controlling the filter bubble through interactive visualization: a user study. *Proceedings of the 25th ACM conference on Hypertext and social media*; 2014 September; Santiago, Chile. New York: Association for Computing Machinery.
- [24] OECD. *PISA 2018 Assessment and Analytical Framework*. Paris: OECD Publishing; 2019.
- [25] Selwyn N, Pangrazio L. Doing data differently? Developing personal data tactics and strategies amongst young mobile media users. *Big Data & Society* 2018; 5(1): 1–12.
- [26] Cook-Sather A, Bovill C, Felten P. *Engaging Students as Partners in Learning and Teaching: A Guide for Faculty*. San Francisco: Jossey Bass; 2014.
- [27] Eisenberg, M. B. & Berkowitz, R. E. *Information problem-solving: the big six skills approach*; 2003.

- [28] Prediger S, Link M, Hinz R, Hußmann S, Thiele J, Ralle B. Lehr-Lernprozesse initiieren und erforschen – Fachdidaktische Entwicklungsforschung im Dortmunder Modell. *MNU* 2012; 65(8): 452–457.
- [29] Peffers K, Tuunanen T, Gengler C E, Rossi M, Hui W, Virtanen V et al. The design science research process: a model for producing and presenting information systems research. In *Proceedings of the 1st international conference on design science research in information systems and technology* 2006; 83–106.
- [30] Platz M. „Forscher spielen“ und mathematisches Beweisen in der Primarstufe. *transfer Forschung - Schule* 2020; 6: 30–43.